

Boydadaev Murodjon

Researcher of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

As a result of the rapid development of the world economy during the technological revolution, the debate among economists about the contribution of enterprises of all sizes to economic development has intensified. Theories about the role of small business in the economy have been developed since the 1900s. Schumpeter saw small firms as a collection point for innovation and change in the economic system. However, later in 1942, Schumpeter wrote that it is necessary to accept that large enterprises have become the most powerful engine of development. The change in Schumpeter's position can be explained in terms of long-wave theory [1]. In fact, the fourth long wave (1930-1975) saw the expansion of enterprises in the development of mass production technologies. The effect of economies of scale in production has been recognized as a decisive factor in determining economic efficiency.

That is why many scientists and politicians in this period considered large enterprises to be the driving force of economic development. However, the 1970s saw a decline in the efficiency of large enterprises as recessionary trends intensified. In the 1980s, when demand was saturated with mass-produced products based on fourth-wave technologies, the focus shifted from mass production to individualization. These factors have served to strengthen the small business sector, which is flexible and responsive to changing conditions and consumer demand. This trend is also confirmed in the case of the US economy. In the 1970s and 1980s, large companies in the ferrous metallurgy, automotive, and textile industries in the United States weakened and were aggravated by the pressure of foreign competitors [2]. On the contrary, the position of small business has been strengthened due to the growing

role of the service sector in the US economy. The idea of the decisive contribution of small business to the development of the economy is widespread today, even in the era of the birth of another technological revolution.

A. Alexandrova and K. In the article "Small research and production enterprises - the locomotive of the Russian economy", Borisova points out that small business is one of the main elements of the market economy and affects the rate of economic growth and the composition of the gross domestic product [3]. They also point out that small enterprises have higher labor productivity, they are able to produce new technology and products at a lower cost, and at the same time they provide more employment. L.Gishkaeva believes that small business plays a major role in ensuring the balance between market efficiency and solving social problems, and at the regional level - in reducing the unemployment rate, increasing the income of the population, and increasing the budget income [4].

E.N. According to Sirota, the state's neglect of the interests of entrepreneurs leads to their inadequate response to the influence of management [5]. In order to improve the state management of entrepreneurship, it is necessary to increase the awareness of the state bodies about the real situation at the microeconomic level and take measures that take into account the reality, not the mythical structure of entrepreneurship. This allows for the development of more adequate management solutions, including the regulatory and legal basis of activities of micro-level economic entities. In particular, it will be possible to equalize the operating conditions of different business segments by introducing uniform conditions for minimum mandatory social insurance in all forms for all resident individuals, which is gradually approaching the practice of developed countries.

V.V. Ivanov points to the uncertainty of the role of small businesses in the economy. The cases where small businesses in science-intensive industries can provide mass consumer goods (if you don't consider the IT industry) are the exception rather than the rule [6]. For small enterprises engaged in the creation of

technologies, a consumer is required, which should be large production structures capable of providing mass production. The absence of an end consumer clearly indicates the impossibility of business expansion. There is no unity in the positions of foreign scientists regarding the contribution of small and large business to economic development. So, to answer the question of what size of business contributes the most to economic development, economists have tried to find a relationship between the size of firms and their ability to innovate.

REFERENCES

1. Mullabaev, B. B. (2018). Econometric Analysis Of Vertical Integration Of The Light Industry Enterprises Of The Namangan Region (On The Example Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan). *Scientific Review: Theory and Practice*, (8), 22, 36.
2. Mullabayev, B. B. (2018). Economic analysis of vertical integration of the Namangan region (on the prerogative of the Republic of Uzbekistan). *Science of theory: theory and practice"-8*.
3. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT. *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*, 2, 1-9.
4. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). Development Of Innovative Activities Of Enterprises On The Basis Of Vertical Integration Processes. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(10), 5020-5031.
5. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). Challenges of Digital Educational Environment. *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*, 4, 54-60.
6. Mallaboyev, N. M., Sharifjanovna, Q. M., & Nodirbek, M. (2022, May). INTERACTION BETWEEN INFORMATION COMPLEXES IN ECONOMIC SPHERES. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 250-253).
7. Шерматов Г.Г. Основные аспекты совершенствования структуры управления в акционерных обществах. "Экономический вестник Узбекистана" журнал. 2002 год №4 55-56 стр.

8. Shermatov G'.G'. [PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES - AS AN
OBJECT OF MANAGEMENT](#) «Экономика и социум» №2(81) часть 1 (февраль,
2021). Сайт :<http://www.iupr.ru>

9. Shermatov G'.G'. SITUATIONAL APPROACHES TO EFFECTIVE
LEADERSHIP «Экономика и социум» №3(82) часть 1 (март, 2021). Сайт:
<http://www.iupr.ru>